

NAHEP

THE WORLD BANK

National Conference on NEP-2020

For

**Comprehensive Transformation in Agricultural Education - initiatives,
challenges and a way forward**

15-16 March, 2022

SOUVENIR

Dr. D. M. Chandargi

Director of Extension & Organizing Secretary

**UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES
Raichur - 584 104, Karnataka, India**

Ph: 08532-220152 Toll Free No. 1800 4250 470

e-mail: nahepig@uasraichur.edu.in

www.uasraichur.edu.in

Accessibility of ICT tools for Digital Agricultural Education in National Education Policy-2020

Nasratullah* Manjula. N.** and S.S.Dolli***

Ph.D Scholar* Professor** and Professor***

University of Agricultural Sciences Dharwad
Department of Agricultural Extension Education
Email: nasratkakar3@gmail.com

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are defined as all digital devices, tools, content, resources, forums, and services, as well as those that can be converted into or delivered through digital forms that can be deployed to achieve the goals of teaching and learning, improving access to and reach of resources and educational system management. These will include not only computer hardware and software applications, but also interactive digital content, internet and other satellite communication devices, radio and television services, web-based content repositories, interactive forums and learning management systems. Different ICT tools are stated to help improve access to education, enhance educational quality, strengthen the relevance of education to the increasingly digital workplace and help transform teaching and learning into an engaging, active process related to real life when utilized effectively. The integration of ICT into educational systems, on the other hand, ranges from the basic use of technology to help instruction (e.g., power point presentations) to the delivery of whole courses or programmes using ICT (e.g., MOOCs). However, students' ICT ownership, access, abilities, and amount and kind of use are all important factors in incorporating ICTs into their education. Desktop computers, projectors, and photocopiers are some examples of ICT resources. If these resources are not available in Institutions, it can prevent effective use of ICT in classrooms. The study conducted in UAS, Dharwad regarding accessibility of faculty and students to various ICT tools. Study revealed that (50%) faculty were have medium level access to various ICT tools followed by (30%) and (20%) high level and low level accessibility respectively. In case of students also, medium level access to ICT tools were more (40%) followed by low (36%) and high level (24%) accessibility respectively. So there is ample scope for adopting ICTs in teaching and learning on farm Universities under NEP-2020.